

Forensic Insights Into Toxic Or Lethal Exposure: Examining The Impact Of Availability On Impulsive Suicide In Rural Maharashtra

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Abstract:

Pesticide-related suicide is a critical, enduring health issue in agrarian and developing regions, often stemming from easy access to highly toxic substances. In rural Maharashtra, the widespread accessibility of lethal substances significantly shapes method selection during impulsive suicidal crises. While Forensic toxicology identifies the specific chemical agents used, a focus on psychological impulsivity is essential to understand the underlying behavioural intent and decision-making processes. An evidence-based assessment of the relationship between easy access to pesticides, individual impulsivity, and the incidence of impulsive suicidal behaviour among rural residents aged 25-45 years was examined in Pune district, Maharashtra. Researchers reviewed on poisoning, mental health, and public safety reports. At the same time, a survey was conducted to see how easily people get pesticides and how they store them at home. Impulsivity was assessed using a validated direct impulsiveness scale i.e., BIS-11, and its association with accessibility variables was analysed to determine behavioural vulnerability. It is proposed that high pesticide availability, combined with heightened impulsivity, significantly increases the risk of impulsive self-poisoning, in such access, method selection is driven by immediate access rather than toxicological awareness. Chemical toxicity is not directly proportional to suicidal intent, as environmental and emotional factors often drive behaviour. Medico-legal interpretation, which merges toxicological findings with psychological evaluation, is essential for distinguishing impulsive suicide from accidental ingestion. This puts the emphasis on the importance of preventive measures like safe chemical storage and rural mental health services.

Keywords: Pesticide, Suicide, Impulsiveness, Agrarian and Preventive Measures.

Introduction:

Some chemical or biological substances are used to prevent, destroy, repel or control pests like insects, weeds, fungi, rodents and other organisms which harm crops, stored food, livestock and human health are termed as Pesticides. In rural agricultural settings, with the easy access to highly toxic substances like

pesticides, pesticide-related suicide is observed to be a critical, enduring health issue.

The presence of easily accessible toxic chemicals within agrarian households in rural India constitutes a considerable public health concern. Data from the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB, 2023) indicates that poisoning, often involving pesticides, is a primary method of

suicide, leading to considerable mortality in agricultural states like Maharashtra. The availability of lethal pesticides in rural homes often dictates the method selected during impulsive suicidal behaviour. Reduced capacity for foresight and impulsive, rapid reactions are key drivers of suicidal risk. The BIS-11 survey is a reliable way to measure how impulsive someone is. If highly impulsive people have easy access to dangerous pesticides, the chances of them attempting self-poisoning on impulse are high. Forensic toxicology can identify the poison used, but it cannot determine whether it was an intentional act. Integrating psychological and toxicological findings improves the interpretation of pesticide deaths. Accordingly, this study examines how the interaction between easy pesticide availability and impulsivity drives impulsive suicide risk among rural populations in Maharashtra.

Sl. No.	State/UT	Other Self-employed Persons				Persons Engaged in Farming Sector (Total)				Persons Engaged in Farming Sector (Farmers/Cultivators (Total))			
		Male	Female	Trans-gender	Total	Male	Female	Trans-gender	Total	Male	Female	Trans-gender	Total
(1)	(2)	(63)	(64)	(65)	(66)	(67)	(68)	(69)	(70)	(71)	(72)	(73)	(74)
STATES													
1	ANDHRA PRADESH	663	79	0	742	828	97	0	925	195	6	0	201
2	ARUNACHAL PRADESH	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	ASSAM	40	17	0	57	97	19	0	116	39	0	0	39
4	BIHAR	45	2	0	47	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	CHHATTISGARH	59	31	0	90	414	54	0	468	73	0	0	73
6	GOA	11	1	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	GUJARAT	387	10	0	397	128	13	0	141	1	0	0	1
8	HARYANA	152	15	0	207	89	9	0	98	0	0	0	0
9	HIMACHAL PRADESH	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	JHARKHAND	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	KARNATAKA	498	63	1	562	2241	182	0	2423	1385	40	0	1425
12	KERALA	568	37	0	605	119	13	0	132	3	0	0	3
13	MADHYA PRADESH	636	29	0	665	701	76	0	777	94	0	0	94
14	MAHARASHTRA	669	25	0	694	3501	250	0	4151	2441	77	0	2518
15	MANIPUR	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
16	MEGHALAYA	0	0	0	0	19	1	0	20	13	1	0	14
17	MIZORAM	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
18	NAGALAND	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
19	ODISHA	326	49	0	375	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
20	PUNJAB	71	1	1	73	174	0	0	174	141	0	0	141
21	RAJASTHAN	123	18	0	141	227	23	0	250	0	0	0	0
22	SIKKIM	16	1	0	17	6	0	0	6	0	0	0	0
23	TAMIL NADU	914	48	0	962	587	44	0	631	60	7	0	67
24	TELANGANA	964	97	0	1061	54	2	0	56	54	2	0	56
25	TRIPURA	5	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
26	UTTAR PRADESH	331	13	0	344	342	15	0	357	33	3	0	36
27	UTTARAKHAND	17	2	0	19	7	0	0	7	0	0	0	0
28	WEST BENGAL	444	68	0	512	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
TOTAL (STATES)		6979	606	2	7587	9934	798	0	10732	4532	136	0	4668
UNION TERRITORIES													
29	A & N ISLANDS	12	0	0	12	6	0	0	6	6	0	0	6
30	CHANDIGARH	9	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
31	D & N HAVELI AND DAMAN & DIU	1	1	0	2	22	2	0	24	14	1	0	15
32	DELHI (UT)	163	13	0	176	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
33	JAMMU & KASHMIR	8	5	0	13	13	0	0	13	0	0	0	0
34	LADAKH	2	1	0	3	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
35	LAKSHADWEEP	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
36	PUDUCHERRY	32	1	0	33	10	0	0	10	0	0	0	0
TOTAL (UTS)		227	21	0	248	52	2	0	54	21	1	0	22
TOTAL (ALL INDIA)		7206	627	2	7835	9986	800	0	10786	4553	137	0	4690

Note: Farmer/Cultivator are those whose profession is farming and include those who cultivate on their own land as well as those who cultivate on leased land/other's land with or without the assistance of agricultural labourers. This data depicts only profession of persons who have committed suicide and has no linkage whatsoever regarding cause of suicide.

* As per data provided by States/UTs.

Figure 1- The NCRB Crime in India Report, 2023 showing the number of farmer suicides in India

Review of Literature:

The World Health Organization has stated in their reports that pesticide poisoning can be estimated to be a substantial part of global suicides, particularly in areas where chemicals related to agriculture are easily available and accessible (WHO, 2019). There are studies that tells us that when there is easy access available for lethal means, individuals that have acute psychological distress are more likely to act on suicidal impulses due to means being within reach leading to easier decision making (Gunnell & Eddleston, 2003; Hawton et al., 2012).

Gunnell et al. (2017) has reported that putting nationwide bans on certain highly toxic pesticides in several countries led to notable declines in pesticide ingestion suicides without a corresponding increase in alternative methods.

Socioeconomic stressors such as agricultural debt, crop failure, climate variability and unstable income often contribute to psychological distress among rural populations.

Research has consistently linked impulsivity with suicidal behaviour, particularly in individuals who engage in impulsive suicide attempts during periods of intense emotional distress (Klonsky & May, 2015). The Barratt Impulsiveness Scale (BIS-11) is one of the most widely used psychometric tools for measuring impulsivity in psychological research (Patton et al., 1995). Successive research conducted by Stanford et al. (2009) reviewed the development of the scale.

Forensic toxicology plays a crucial role in identifying the chemical agents involved in poisoning cases. However, toxicological findings alone cannot always determine whether the ingestion was accidental, intentional or impulsive. Integrating Forensic psychology with toxicological data may therefore improve the interpretation of such cases.

Research Gap:

While prior studies have established that easy access to toxic substances increases the likelihood of self-harm, there is limited research examining the combined influence of pesticide availability and individual traits such as impulsivity. Additionally, existing research does not focus on specific locations that has reported high number of farmer suicides like Maharashtra. Therefore, examining the relationship between pesticide availability and impulsivity is essential for addressing the growing concern of suicide in rural agrarian communities especially in the state like Maharashtra where many families are still totally dependent on agriculture as their means of income.

Objectives of The Study:

1. Contextualizing the 'Easy Access' Factor: Household pesticide storage and intentional self-harm in Pune district of Maharashtra in young adults aged 25-45.
2. To examine the association between impulsivity and the choice of self-harm method, with a specific focus on whether high impulsivity increases vulnerability to pesticide ingestion during emotional crises.
3. Merging Forensic toxicology with psychological profiling, to better distinguish suicide from accidents in pesticide deaths.

Hypothesis:

In rural Maharashtra, among adults aged 25-45, easy access to household pesticides combined with higher impulsivity levels significantly increases the risk of impulsive pesticide ingestion during episodes of acute emotional distress.

Research Methodology:

Tools/Instruments:

1. BIS-11(Barratt Impulsiveness Scale,11th Revision,1995)
2. Pesticide availability questionnaire (Self/Author developed with help of ChatGPT)

Research design: Survey based.

Sample size: 50

Sampling method: A non-probability convenience sampling

Ethical Statement:

For data collection to be carried out, approval was obtained from the Research and Ethics Committee of the institute (Ref. No. IFSM/2025-26/R&D-Ethical Committee/07) dated 16-02-2026, covering participant information, informed consent and documentation including geotagged photographs, etc.

Figure 2- Participants being instructed and answering the survey questions

Results:

Table 1- Descriptive Statistics

Tests	N	Mean	SD	Min.	Max.	Range	
BIS- Scale	11	50	65.58	8.19	48	80	32
Pesticide Availability	50	21.70	4.15	13	28	15	

According to the survey of 50 households, the mean pesticide availability score (21.70 ± 4.15) suggests the majority of respondents have easy access to pesticides, with total scores ranging between 13 and 28 out of 30, indicating widespread accessibility within rural households.

Graph 1- Impulsivity frequency

BIS-11 assessment scores (65.58 ± 8.19) indicates that most participants fall within the normal impulsivity range i.e., 36 participants demonstrated normal impulsivity levels, 2 showed low impulsivity, and 12 participants exhibited high impulsivity.

Graph 2- Negative association between pesticide availability and impulsivity

Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to assess the relationship between pesticide availability and impulsivity. The results indicated a moderate negative correlation between the two variables ($r = -.35$), suggesting that higher pesticide availability was associated with slightly lower impulsivity scores. The linear regression analysis was done to determine whether pesticide availability predicts impulsivity or not. However, it accounted for only 12% of the variance in impulsivity scores ($R^2 = .12$), remaining 88% may be due to other factors.

Overall, statistical analysis demonstrates that there is a modest negative association between pesticide availability and impulsivity, with limited predictive strength.

Discussion:

The current research aims to determine whether increased pesticide accessibility intensifies the risk of self-harm in highly impulsive individuals, focusing on rural Maharashtra adults in the Pune district that are aged 25-45 years. The study shows how spatial access and psychological vulnerability drive behavioural risks for farmers. The ‘Means Matter’ principle posits that controlling access to specific, high-lethality methods – rather than just addressing the intent behind a behaviour – can significantly improve public health outcomes (Mann et al., 2005; World Health Organization [WHO], 2014).

A key takeaway is that rural households have unrestricted and consistent access to pesticides. High pesticide availability scores indicate that most participants possess easy access to agricultural chemicals, often operating without structured safety protocols (Eddleston et al., 2002; Gunnell et al., 2017).

Because pesticides are frequently stored in kitchens and living spaces without adequate restrictions, they have become embedded within the home environment, posing significant risks to rural families, especially in farming households (Eddleston et al., 2002).

Availability here implies a high-risk environment characterized by poor storage, improper handling practices, and minimal oversight at the household level. A swift transition from distress to injurious action often occurs when environmental safeguards are absent, reinforcing the understanding that protecting individuals from themselves requires reducing immediate access to dangerous actions (WHO, 2014; Zalsman et al., 2016).

Despite high pesticide accessibility, impulsivity levels among participants showed variability. BIS-11 assessment results indicated that while the majority of individuals fell within

the normal range, a smaller proportion exhibited low or high impulsivity. Rather than mere prevalence, the danger of impulsivity is its interaction with environmental hazards. The number of participants was 50. The results revealed a moderate negative correlation between pesticide availability and impulsivity ($r = -.35$), indicating that higher levels of pesticide availability were associated with slightly lower impulsivity scores.

To further examine this relationship, a linear regression analysis was conducted to assess whether pesticide availability could significantly predict impulsivity. The findings showed that pesticide availability accounted for only 12% of the variance in impulsivity scores ($R^2 = .12$), suggesting that the majority of the variance (88%) is likely influenced by other unmeasured factors.

Participants with high impulsivity also demonstrated poor pesticide management, indicating that this trait drives both risky decision-making and behaviours that increase environmental exposure (Klonsky & May, 2015). Findings also reveal that impulsivity acts as a behavioural hazard when paired with readily available toxic substances, leading to rash, emotion-driven actions. Under extreme stress, this tendency is amplified, particularly, in rural Maharashtra, where systemic agricultural debt and climate-driven crises place immense pressure on individuals. This reflects a “cascading stress” scenario (When it rains, it pours), where compounding economic and personal pressures dismantle the psychological capacity to cope (Patel et al., 2012; National Crime Records Bureau [NCRB], 2023).

When people are in an acute emotional crisis, such as a major fight or financial ruin, they experience intense emotions, narrow thinking, and poor problem-solving abilities. This emotional state often leads to acting on impulse without thinking about the future. In these

moments, foresight is diminished, and if dangerous items like pesticides are kept in the home, the chance of a fatal, impulsive action increases. This shows that high emotional distress combined with easy access to harmful methods drastically increases the danger of self-harm (Baumeister, 1990; Shneidman, 1993).

Rural landscapes, defined by fragmented healthcare and delayed emergency response, turn poisoning cases into medical crises where time lost is life lost. These geographical challenges, combined with high accessibility to toxins, mean that rural settings significantly exacerbate fatality risks compared to areas with better infrastructure (WHO, 2019).

The relationship between impulsivity and the accessibility of pesticides can be seen as a situation where psychological traits and environmental factors amplify each other. Research indicates that their selection of immediate availability rather than a planned toxicological choice (Gunnell et al., 2017). This reinforces the idea that impulsive acts are often shaped by the immediate environment and situational factors rather than long-term deliberation.

Behavioural analysis highlights a critical link between high impulsivity and poor safety adherence. Individuals prone to impulsive actions are less likely to implement safeguards like restricted access or proper labelling, escalating both the risk of intentional self-harm and unintentional poisoning. Consequently, adopting a proactive ‘prevention-first’ approach is essential to mitigating both types of hazards (Zalsman et al., 2016).

Rural mental health is often compromised by high stigma and the internalization of distress because help-seeking is discouraged, emotional crises escalate privately, illustrating the “still waters run deep” phenomenon. This combination of suppressed turmoil, high impulsivity, and

available lethal means significantly elevates the risk of impulsive self-harm (WHO, 2014).

The forensic interpretation of pesticide-related deaths is often constrained by a reliance on quantitative data alone. Although toxicology identifies the poison, it rarely reveals the intent, creating a gap between forensic findings and the legal determination of the manner of death.

To bridge this gap, incorporating subjective elements- like the victim's recent behaviour and environmental factors- is crucial. Effective forensic investigation requires integrating these intangible factors with standard analytical techniques.

In rural areas, distinguishing accidental from intentional poisoning requires an integrated strategy, recognizing that accessibility, behavioural tendencies, and stressors are intertwined.

This approach affirms that combining psychological assessment with toxicology yields a more complete picture, supporting the principle that the collective evidence is greater than the sum of its parts.

The findings emphasize the critical role of environmental interventions, specifically safe storage practices, which serve as essential barriers to delay action and facilitate emotional de-escalation. By acting as a preventive measure that averts severe consequences, these strategies are vital. Alongside this, improving rural mental health resources and fostering a culture of help-seeking behaviour are necessary steps to mitigate risk (WHO, 2014; Gunnell et al., 2017).

Despite being limited in scope and descriptive in nature, this study offers critical insights into pesticide self-poisoning in rural Maharashtra, underscoring the often impulsive and preventable nature of these acts. The findings underscore that recognizing this phenomenon demands proactive responsibility. Effective mitigation necessitates holistic efforts integrating

strict environmental control, psychological support systems, and community-level interventions.

Conclusion:

The present study highlights that if forensic psychology is integrated with toxicological data, it may help in enhancement of the ability to differentiate between intentional self-harm and accidental ingestion. The following measures can be taken- safe storage for agricultural toxic chemicals with structured safety measures and community education to reduce easy access to toxic substances. Given the connection between impulsivity and risk, improving mental health screenings in rural areas is recommended. The study supports an integrated strategy that combines environmental management with targeted psychological care.

Limitation:

Location for the sample collection is limited to specific region of Maharashtra.

Additional Supplementary Information: [Link](#)

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